

PSYCHOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

Mukhammadieva Risola Kyrgyzboy Kyzi

Teacher of Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

Abstract: The article is dedicated to one of the famed issues occurred in teaching foreign languages. Author states about psychological factors in high education, mainly in freshmen who could face with psychological barriers rather than linguistic one. And states teachers' role in adaptation period of the student. Gives clearly statements and justifications about modern methods of teaching foreign languages and its importance to overcome above mentioned problems.

Key words: communicative culture, psychological discomfort, dissatisfaction, second language, speech skills, communicative method.

It is acknowledged that the methodology of teaching foreign languages is based on the laws established by philosophy, psychology, physiology, linguistics, pedagogy and is associated with many certain difficulties. In the psychological and pedagogical literature, the difficulties associated with the emergence and functioning of the mechanisms of thinking in the first and second languages, as well as the role of mechanical memory and age characteristics in the assimilation of foreign languages are highlighted.

An analysis of the development of psychological science allows us to state that even in the XIX century, the founder of experimental psychology, W. Wundt, determined the correlation between the psychology of speech and feelings. Based on the approach of W. Wundt, patterns have been established in psychological science that manifest themselves both in the assimilation and mastery of foreign languages, and in the study of any subject. [1] Consider as an example the patterns identified by G.E. Wedel:

- the theory of unity of consciousness and activity;
- the theory of the step-by-step formation of mental processes;
- installation theory;
- the concept of an open and hidden way of learning;
- the theory of the degree of intensity of the state of excitation of students in the learning process;
- the concept of inner speech and latent articulation, the basic mechanism of both verbal and figurative thinking;
- the theory of latent verbalization, which governs the neurodynamics of mental processes and much more. [2]

As it is known, the main means of transmitting cultural values, the repository and translator of culture is language. The importance of communicative culture in all social areas, especially in education, is obvious, since here the linguistic competence of a person is formed, which determines the functioning of language in all spheres of life. As noted in the work [2] in the conditions of the modern globalizing world, communicative culture also acts as a way to preserve ethno-cultural identity.

The current stage of development of society is characterized by the need to study foreign languages. Life itself has put a person in conditions where knowledge of one or more foreign languages helps him adapt to a rapidly changing world. The traditional method of teaching foreign languages is aimed at developing reading and translation skills, but not at developing oral speech skills. In this article, we attempt to analyze the teaching of foreign languages, on the example of teaching English at the Navoi State Pedagogical Institute.

One of the main, universally recognized in the world methods of teaching foreign languages is the communicative method. The essence of the communicative method is the simultaneous development of basic language skills (oral and written speech, grammar, reading and listening or listening) in the process of lively, relaxed communication. To teach a student to communicate in a foreign language is the main task of the teacher. Vocabulary, grammatical structures, expressions of a foreign language are presented to the student in the context of a real, emotionally colored situation, which contributes to the quick and lasting memorization of the material being studied.

The communicative method involves the destruction of the psychological barrier between the teacher and the student. And when students no longer feel the "distance" between themselves and the teacher, when they are interested, fun and pleasant to communicate with him - it is easier for them to start talking in a foreign language. Numerous game elements in teaching bring liveliness to the classes, support the positive emotional mood of students, strengthen their motivation. Work "in pairs", "in threes", participation in discussions on topics of interest to students - all this allows the teacher to take into account the individual characteristics of students, make classes creative and exciting, and at the same time gives the teacher the opportunity to exercise full control over the learning process imperceptibly for students.

The modern world is characterized by a tendency to increase people's interest in learning foreign languages. Today, it is almost impossible to imagine a successful person who does not speak at least a basic level of one or even several languages. A foreign language gradually passes from an optional course into the main subject, which is due to objective necessity. However, it should be emphasized that having become the reality of the time, the foreign language, nevertheless, has not received sufficient impetus to spread among the population not engaged in education, or in any sphere

related to international business (for example, tourism). At the same time, it cannot be said that there is no understanding in society of the importance of knowing a foreign language. Most likely, understanding and realizing the need to learn a foreign language, people are often psychologically not ready for reality, which primarily requires continuous work on the language. It is this moment that becomes the most difficult for people who are not connected in their daily activities with the need to communicate with carriers of a foreign culture.

Experience in the Navoi State Pedagogical Institute, long-term observations of the activities of students allow us to state the presence of multiple problems in their study of foreign languages. First of all, it should be noted the difficulties that arise in first-year students. The first year of study at the institute, the change of the social situation, the entry into adulthood, the need to adapt to student life - this is an incomplete list of problems that cause psychological discomfort in young people. To these problems, you can add the difficulties of teaching foreign languages, especially in the absence of the necessary school base.

It should also be noted that not always professional choice is made by young people consciously, often it happens on the recommendation of parents, older friends, teachers. Therefore, the laborious process of working on the language, the lack of independence and self-organization cause disappointment and a feeling of dissatisfaction with the learning process and its results.

Thus, the teacher faces a problem that must be solved taking into account factors that are often not included in the scope of his professional duties. However, first of all, it is necessary to interest students, to turn language lessons into an exciting process, during which, of course, students will have to overcome such difficulties as the language barrier, fear of making a mistake, being misunderstood or causing ridicule. Their overcoming will be facilitated by the friendly atmosphere created by the teacher in the classroom, the atmosphere of mutual support and understanding. Very effective in this regard, in our opinion, is project activity, work in groups on a common task, when the final result depends on each individually and on all together. The selection of topics should be carried out not only in accordance with the curriculum, but also taking into account the interests of students. Their authenticity and relevance are also important.

Another important factor is the use of modern technical means in the classroom, with the help of which it is possible to diversify classes and involve all students in the work, regardless of their level of knowledge. Classes tied to the textbook are no longer relevant. Current students are more willing to work with different gadgets, to search for information they use the Internet, in which they are very well oriented, prefer to take tests or do exercises online, watch videos and movies in the language. To give students the opportunity to show their own imagination and creativity, you can give,

for example, the task to shoot a video voiced in the language on a certain topic, watch it in class, discuss, find mistakes and offer your own options for voicing the video.

The participation of students in the work of language clubs is also quite effective. Here, however, it is necessary to take into account the fact that the members of the club are students with different language levels, which at first leads to difficulties in communication. In this regard, it is possible to hold the first meetings of the clubs on different days, gathering students with the same level of language in groups. Then, gradually, groups can be mixed, emphasizing that the number of students with a lower level of language still prevails. It will take time to unite all, albeit small, groups, but students will already be more liberated linguistically and will be able to easily communicate on an equal footing.

There are many methods and techniques for teaching and learning a foreign language, but still the most effective is complete language immersion, which is impossible without being in a foreign language environment. Students of the faculties of foreign languages simply need to spend some time in the country of the studied language. These can be both short-term internships / courses or summer schools, and semester scholarships. In order to provide students with the opportunity to travel to another country for language practice, it is necessary to establish contacts with foreign universities, conclude cooperation agreements providing for the exchange of students and teachers, organize inter-university scientific and practical conferences and develop joint projects.

Summing up all of the above, it should be emphasized that after all, success in learning a foreign language, and any other subject, by 80% depends on the student himself. Very often you can hear reproaches against teachers who allegedly cannot interest students in their subject or are quite interesting and accessible to present educational material. Of course, such problems exist, but it seems to us that they are not decisive. The teacher sets a certain vector for the student's work, offers, but in no case, does not impose, his methodology. Each individual himself determines whether the proposed path of training suits him, he can use or refuse the proposed path, he can adopt an acceptable and interesting approach for him. The main thing in all this is self-interest.

References:

1. W. Wundt: “Principles of physiological psychology” 1904.
2. Ведель Г. Е.: “Истории методов преподавания иностранных языков.” Воронеж, Изд-во Воронеж, ун-та, 1979. 56 с.